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Phyto-Larvicides: Evaluating the Effectiveness of four Acetone Leaf Extracts on *Aedes aegypti* Larvae

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Abstract *Aedes aegypti* is widely recognized as the primary vector responsible for the transmission of several viral diseases, including dengue, Zika, chikungunya, and urban yellow fever. Targeting mosquito larvae is considered the most effective approach for mosquito control compared to other methods. Plant-derived insecticides are favoured over synthetic ones due to their environmental friendliness, affordability, specificity to target pests, and reduced toxicity to non-target organisms. This study aimed to assess the larvicidal activity of acetone leaf extracts from four locally available and cost-effective plant species i.e., *Saraca indica*, *Lawsonia inermis*, *Dalbergia sissoo*, and *Punica granatum* against fourth instar larvae of *Aedes aegypti*. Each plant extract was tested at three concentrations (1%, 1.5%, and 2%), and larval mortality was recorded after 24, 48, and 72 hours. Results showed a dose- and time-dependent increase in mortality rates. All extracts produced notable larvicidal effects at 1.5% and 2% concentrations, while the 1% concentration failed to produce significant mortality even after 72 hours. After 72 hours of exposure, the highest mortality (100%) was observed with 2% concentrations of *Saraca indica* and *Lawsonia inermis*. Additionally, *Saraca indica* showed 96.51% mortality at 2% concentration after just 48 hours, and *Dalbergia sissoo* also showed significant mortality (96.51%) after 72 hours. To further evaluate the effectiveness of these extracts, LC₅₀ and LC₉₀ values were calculated at 24, 48, and 72 hours. *Saraca indica* exhibited the lowest LC₅₀ (1.51, 1.28, 1.14) and LC₉₀ (2.08, 1.86, 1.52) values, indicating the highest larvicidal potency. In contrast, *Eucalyptus rudis* showed relatively higher LC₅₀ and LC₉₀ values, suggesting it was moderately toxic to *Aedes aegypti* larvae.

Keywords *Aedes aegypti*, larvicidal activity, *Saraca indica*, *Lawsonia inermis*, *Dalbergia sissoo*, *Punica granatum*, LC50, LC90.

Introduction The *Aedes aegypti* mosquito is a major vector responsible for the transmission of several significant viral diseases, including dengue fever, Zika virus, chikungunya, and urban yellow fever. (WHO, 2019, Musso et al., 2015, Pialoux et al., 2007, Monath, 2001). Native to tropical and subtropical regions of Africa, this mosquito has since spread worldwide due to human activities such as international travel and trade, making it a global health concern (Gubler, 2001). The adult female mosquito is particularly notable for its need to feed on blood for egg development. During blood-feeding, *Aedes aegypti* tends to bite during the day, with peak activity occurring during early morning and late afternoon (Carter et al., 2000). The mosquito is a persistent feeder, capable of biting several hosts in a single blood meal. One of the most distinguishing features of *Aedes aegypti* is its preference for domestic environments, where it thrives near humans. *Aedes aegypti* mosquito is highly adapted to urban environments, breeding in small containers of stagnant water commonly found in residential areas, such as discarded tires, water storage containers, and flower pots (Reiter, 2001). This makes its control particularly challenging, as it relies on urban infrastructure that is difficult to manage (Kraemer et al., 2015).

Objective of study To explore the potential of additional plant-based larvicides, the present study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of acetone leaf extracts from four affordable and easily available native plant species: *Saraca indica* (Ashoka tree), *Lawsonia inermis* (Heena tree), *Dalbergia sissoo* (Indian rosewood), and *Punica granatum* (Pomegranate tree) against *Aedes aegypti* mosquitoes. The findings of this research are expected to contribute to the development of sustainable strategies for controlling *Aedes aegypti* populations.

Review of Literature

The primary methods of controlling the mosquito population include the use of chemical insecticides, biological control agents (such as the introduction of mosquito-eating fish), and genetic strategies, such as the release of genetically modified mosquitoes (Harris et al., 2012). However, the widespread use of chemical insecticides has led to resistance in mosquito populations, making the control of *Aedes aegypti* increasingly difficult (Ranson et al., 2010). Moreover, climate change is expected to expand the geographical range of *Aedes aegypti*, increasing the risk of disease transmission in areas previously free from these mosquito-borne illnesses (Patz et al., 2005). This has underscored the need for sustainable, environmentally friendly alternatives to traditional chemical control methods, such as the use of plant-based insecticides, which are gaining attention as potential tools for mosquito control (Ahmed et al., 2021; Iqbal et al., 2021; Gosh et al., 2012; Muhammed et al., 2022). Pavela et al. (2019) conducted an extensive review identifying 429 plant species across 101 botanical families that exhibit notable larvicidal activity, with LC₅₀ values under 10 ppm, against prominent mosquito vectors, including those from the *Anopheles*, *Aedes*, and *Culex* genera. Additionally, Rodrigues et al. (2020) analysed the larvicidal potential of 150 plant species from 52 families against *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus*. Further studies by Ahmed et al. (2023), Ajaegbu et al. (2023), and Alvarez-Valverde et al. (2023) have provided additional evidence supporting the use of plant extracts as safe and efficient insecticides against *Aedes aegypti*, reinforcing their applicability in sustainable vector control strategies.

Methodology

Aedes aegypti mosquitoes were reared in 30×30×30 cm cages under controlled lab conditions (26 ± 2°C, 70 ± 5% RH, 12:12 h light/dark cycle) as per Saxena and Yadav (1983). Leaves of test plant species were collected from the Jaipur district, authenticated by a taxonomist, washed, shade-dried for 7 days, and ground into powder. 30 g of powdered leaf material per species underwent Soxhlet extraction with acetone for 8 hours. Extracts were filtered, evaporated, and concentrated to form a residue, which was dissolved in acetone to make a 10% (w/v) stock solution, stored at 4°C. Working concentrations (1%, 1.5%, 2%) were prepared from the stock solution with water and 0.05% Tween-80 was used as an emulsifier. In controls, the same amount of solvent was added to the water at each concentration. 25 fourth instar *A. aegypti* larvae were exposed to each test concentration in 100 ml solution within 500 ml beakers. Each test was done in triplicate with controls, and mortality was recorded at 24, 48, and 72 hours post-exposure using a plastic dropper to separate live and dead larvae. To account for any mortality observed in the control group, the corrected percentage mortality was calculated using Abbott's formula (1987):

$$\text{Corrected Mortality (\%)} = (T - C / 100 - C) \times 100$$

Where: **T** = observed mortality (%) in the treated group

C = observed mortality (%) in the control group

Statistics Used in the Study

To assess the toxicological efficacy of the plant extracts, lethal concentration values—LC₅₀ (lethal concentration to kill 50% of larvae) and LC₉₀ (lethal concentration to kill 90%) were calculated based on larval mortality observed at 24, 48, and 72 hours post-treatment. These metrics are standard indicators in toxicological studies to evaluate the potency of bioactive substances. Mortality data were statistically analysed using two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference (HSD) post hoc test to compare mean differences among treatment groups and exposure times. Furthermore, Probit analysis was conducted to estimate LC₅₀ and LC₉₀ values. All statistical computations were performed using Microsoft Excel. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant, as per the method outlined by Finney (1971).

Result and Discussion

The larvicidal effects of different plant extracts against *Aedes aegypti* larvae are summarized in Table 1 and illustrated in Figures 1 to 4. At a 1% concentration, the corrected mortality rates observed after 24, 48, and 72 hours of exposure were not statistically significant. However, among these testes extracts, *Lawsonia inermis* showed the highest mortality (13.35%, 20.35%, and 34%), followed by *Saraca indica* (6.65%, 13.17%, and 23.91%), *Dalbergia sissoo* (5%, 11.65%, and 13.17%), and *Punica granatum* (3.35%, 6.65%, and 13.35%). At the 1.5% concentration level, *Saraca indica* demonstrated the highest larvicidal activity, recording corrected mortalities of 33.35%, 86.09%, and 92.77% at 24, 48, and 72 hours, respectively. This was followed by *Lawsonia inermis* (30%, 40.62%, 58.34%) and *Dalbergia sissoo* (20%, 36.65%, 65.26%). Interestingly, *Dalbergia* showed slightly greater mortality than *Lawsonia* at the 72-hour mark. *Punica granatum* showed the least efficacy at 1.5%, with mortality rates of 16.65%, 30%, and 40% over the same time intervals. At the highest concentration of 2%, *Saraca indica* proved to be the most potent, achieving 90%, 96.51%, and 100% larval mortality after 24, 48, and 72 hours, respectively. *Dalbergia sissoo* and *Lawsonia inermis* also showed strong larvicidal effects at this concentration, with mortality rates of 80%, 90%,

and 96.51% for *Dalbergia*, and 53.35%, 90%, and 100% for *Lawsonia* after 24, 48 & 72 hrs of treatment respectively. *Punica granatum* exhibited a moderate effect at 2% concentration, resulting in 50%, 63.35%, and 76.65% corrected mortality after 24, 48, and 72 hours. Higher concentrations of these extracts induced observable behavioural changes in the larvae, such as continuous abdominal flickering, semi-circular body bending, drowsiness, and eventual death.

Table no.1:
Percent corrected mortality of three dose levels (1, 1.5 & 2%) of test plant extracts after 24, 48 & 72 hrs exposure time.

Plant Extracts	Percent corrected mortality								
	1% conc.			1.5% conc.			2% conc.		
	24 hrs	48 hrs	72 hrs	24 hrs	48 hrs	72 hrs	24 hrs	48 hrs	72 hrs
<i>Saraca indica</i>	6.65	13.17	23.91	33.35	86.09	92.77	90	96.51	100
<i>Lawsonia inermis</i>	13.35	20.35	34	30	40.65	58.34	53.35	90	100
<i>Dalbergia sisso</i>	5	11.65	13.17	20	36.65	65.26	80	90	96.51
<i>Punica granatum</i>	3.35	6.65	13.35	16.65	20	40	50	63.35	76.65

Fig No.1 : Effect of leaf extract of *Saraca indica* against *Aedes aegypti* leaves

Fig No.2 : Effect of leaf extract of *Lawsonia inermis* against *Aedes aegypti* leaves

Fig No.3 : Effect of leaf extract of *Dalbergia sisso* against *Aedes aegypti* larvae

Fig No.4: Effect of leaf extract of *Punica granatum* against *Aedes aegypti* larvae

The results of the two-way ANOVA analysis (Table 2) clearly demonstrate that larval mortality significantly increases with both higher extract concentrations and longer exposure durations. These effects were statistically significant. Further analysis using Tukey's HSD post hoc test revealed that at the 1% concentration, none of the tested plant extracts exhibited substantial larvicidal activity. However, at 1.5% and 2% concentrations, *Saraca indica* emerged as the most effective extract, followed by *Lawsonia inermis* and *Dalbergia sissoo*. *Punica granatum* showed only moderate larvicidal effects at the highest tested concentration (2%).

Table no.2: Two-way ANOVA test results of different plant extracts according Dose level (1%, 1.5% & 2%) and Treatment duration (24hrs, 48 hrs & 72 hrs).

	<i>Saraca indica</i>		<i>Lawsonia inermis</i>		<i>Dalbergia sissoo</i>		<i>Punica granatum</i>	
	p-value	F-value	p-value	F-value	p-value	F-value	p-value	F-value
Conc.	0.0072	21.520	0.0020	34.966	0.0017	46.49	0.0004	93.190
Time	0.1700	2.846	0.0270	10.122	0.1110	3.996	0.0201	12.008

F crit-6.944 (F-value > F-crit= significant), (p-value > 0.05= significant)

Table 3 presents the LC₅₀ and LC₉₀ values for three concentration levels (1%, 1.5%, and 2%) of each plant extract following 24, 48, and 72 hours of exposure. After 72 hours, *Saraca indica* exhibited the highest larvicidal potency, with the lowest LC₅₀ and LC₉₀ values (1.14 and 1.52), followed by *Lawsonia inermis* (1.20 and 1.68), *Dalbergia sissoo* (1.31 and 1.77), and *Punica granatum* (1.54 and 2.51). A similar trend was observed after 48 hours, with *Saraca* again showing the lowest LC₅₀ (1.28) and LC₉₀ (1.86), followed by

Lawsonia (1.34 and 2.10), *Dalbergia* (1.45 and 2.10), and *Punica* (1.86 and 3.23). However, the pattern differed slightly after 24 hours of exposure. Although *Saraca* maintained the lowest LC₅₀ and LC₉₀ values (1.51 and 2.08), *Dalbergia* (1.65 and 2.39) showed greater toxicity than *Lawsonia* (1.90 and 4.06). While *Punica* recorded the highest LC₅₀ value (2.04), its LC₉₀ value (3.31) was lower than that of *Lawsonia*, indicating moderate larvicidal activity.

Table.3: LC₅₀ and LC₉₀ values (in %) of plant extracts applying three Dose concentrations (1%, 1.5% & 2%) after 24, 48 and 72 h of exposure time.

Plant species	After 24 hrs		After 48 hrs		After 72 hrs	
	LC ₅₀	LC ₉₀	LC ₅₀	LC ₉₀	LC ₅₀	LC ₉₀
<i>Saraca indica</i>	1.51	2.08	1.28	1.86	1.14	1.52
<i>Lawsonia inermis</i>	1.90	4.06	1.34	2.10	1.20	1.68
<i>Dalbergia sisso</i>	1.65	2.39	1.45	2.10	1.31	1.77
<i>Punica granatum</i>	2.04	3.31	1.86	3.23	1.54	2.51

Based on the comparative toxicity analysis, the effectiveness of the plant extracts can be ranked in the following order: *Saraca indica* > *Lawsonia inermis* ≈ *Dalbergia sissoo* > *Punica granatum*.

Discussion:

The present investigation revealed a clear trend of increased larval mortality in *Aedes aegypti* larvae with extended exposure durations across all tested plant extracts. Importantly, the control groups exhibited either no mortality or negligible larval deaths at all observation points, thereby affirming the potent larvicidal efficacy of the tested botanicals. This pattern of heightened mortality, correlated with both concentration and exposure time, highlights a dose-dependent relationship, aligning with previous findings reported by Ahmed et al. (2023), who observed a similar gradient of larvicidal response to increasing doses of plant-derived extracts. Comparable outcomes were documented by Sharma et. al., (2024), wherein the insecticidal activity of aqueous extract of leaves of *Saraca indica* against stored grain insects was found to be directly related to the exposure time and concentration of the aqueous extract.

The toxic effects exerted by these plant extracts are not limited to mortality alone. They also provoke distinct behavioural anomalies in larvae. Observed symptoms included hyperactivity, abdominal twitching, and erratic swimming, followed by sluggishness and an eventual loss of coordination. Affected larvae frequently displayed a curved or cruciform posture and repeatedly surfaced in an attempt to respire, ultimately succumbing due to apparent respiratory failure. Additionally, the formation of larval-pupal intermediates and incidences of mortality during ecdysis were noted, indicating possible disruption of hormonal or developmental processes. These observations are in concordance with those of Neraliya and Srivastava (1996), who reported similar physiological disruptions and insect growth regulator-like effects in *Culex quinquefasciatus* when exposed to some acetone plant extracts. Collectively, these results underline the multifaceted impacts of plant-derived compounds, not only as direct toxicants but also as disruptors of developmental and behavioural homeostasis in mosquito larvae, further validating their potential as eco-friendly alternatives to conventional chemical larvicides.

Specifically, *Saraca sp.* has been identified as an effective larvicide. Sharma et al. (2018) evaluated the bioactivity of aqueous extracts of *Saraca sp.* against third to early fourth instar larvae of *A. aegypti*. The results indicated a dose-dependent larvicidal effect, with an LC₅₀ value of 0.26% and an LC₉₀ value of 0.54% after 24 hours of exposure. Notably, 100% mortality was achieved at a concentration of 0.75%, highlighting the extract's potent efficacy. Another investigation by Mathew et al. (2009) evaluated various solvent extracts of *S. indica* against mosquito larvae. The petroleum ether extract of the leaves and the chloroform extract of the bark exhibited larvicidal activity against *Culex quinquefasciatus*, with LC₅₀ values of 228.9 ppm and 291.5 ppm, respectively. While this study focused on *C. quinquefasciatus*, it underscores the broader insecticidal potential of *S. indica* extracts. They also suggested that, insecticidal potential of plant is mainly attributed to the presence of secondary metabolites like Carbohydrates, saponins, terpenoids, tannins, proteins.

Several studies have validated the larvicidal potential of *L. inermis*. Subramaniam et al. (2012) evaluated methanolic leaf extracts of *L. inermis* against *Aedes aegypti*, *Anopheles stephensi*, and *Culex quinquefasciatus*. The LC₅₀ values ranged between 64.57 ppm to 122.56 ppm after 24 hours of exposure, depending on the mosquito species, indicating strong larvicidal activity. Dass and Mariappan (2014) assessed the larvicidal activity of its leaf extracts on *Culex quinquefasciatus*. Adebayo et al. (2021) confirmed the larvicidal and pupicidal potential of *L. inermis* ethanolic extract against *Anopheles gambiae*, showing progressive mortality with increasing concentrations. These studies found that *Lawsonia inermis* exhibited larvicidal properties, suggesting its potential applicability against other mosquito species, including *Aedes aegypti*. The bio-efficacy of this plant is

mainly attributed to the presence of secondary metabolites like lawsone (2-hydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone), tannins, flavonoids, and saponins, which interfere with the physiological systems of mosquito larvae. (Sandhanam et.al., 2018)

Dalbergia sissoo (Indian rosewood) has demonstrated significant insecticidal properties against various mosquito species, making it a promising candidate for eco-friendly vector control strategies. A study by Ansari et al. (2000) evaluated the larvicidal, growth inhibitory, and repellent effects of *D. sissoo* oil against three mosquito species: *Anopheles stephensi*, *Aedes aegypti*, and *Culex quinquefasciatus*. The oil was applied to water surfaces at concentrations ranging from 0.4 to 5 ml/m². Results indicated a dose-dependent larvicidal activity, with 100% mortality observed in *C. quinquefasciatus* larvae within 24 hours at a concentration of 4 ml/m². *A. aegypti* and *A. stephensi* exhibited 90% and 60% mortality rates, respectively, under the same conditions. Additionally, the oil effectively inhibited pupation and subsequent adult emergence. Sublethal doses (2 ml/m²) led to adults that either did not lay eggs or produced non-viable eggs. The insecticidal efficacy of *D. sissoo* is attributed to its rich phytochemical profile, including compounds such as dalbergin, dalbergenone, and various flavonoids. These constituents are believed to interfere with the nervous system of insects, leading to paralysis and death.

A study evaluated the larvicidal effects of ethanolic extracts from *P. granatum* seeds against third instar larvae of *Aedes aegypti* (Kaur and Kaur, 2019). The results indicated a concentration-dependent mortality as 87.2% mortality was observed at 160 ppm and complete (100%) mortality at 320 ppm conc. after 24 hours. The lethal concentration values (LC₅₀ and LC₉₀) after 24 hours were 84.8 ppm and 177.3 ppm, respectively. These findings suggest the potential of *P. granatum* seed extracts as effective larvicides. Another investigation focused on the larvicidal and repellent activities of ethanolic extracts from *P. granatum* peels against *Anopheles stephensi* and *Culex quinquefasciatus*. (Asif and Kumar, 2011). Using concentrations ranging from 50 to 250 ppm, the study reported significant larval mortality and repellency, highlighting the extract's efficacy as a natural mosquito control agent.

Although direct studies on the larvicidal activity of the tested plant species against *Aedes aegypti* are limited, various extracts derived from different parts of these plants have been documented to possess multiple bioactive properties. These attributes suggest their potential as natural mosquito larvicides. Overall, the findings highlight the promise of these plant extracts as environmentally friendly alternatives to conventional chemical insecticides for managing *Aedes aegypti* populations. Nevertheless, further in-depth research is essential to isolate, identify, and characterize the specific bioactive compounds responsible for the observed larvicidal effects, as well as to assess their safety and effectiveness under real-world field conditions.

Conclusion

The findings of this study suggest that all tested plant extracts possess the potential to be developed into environmentally safe larvicidal agents. Among them, *Saraca indica* followed by *Lawsonia inermis*, *Dalbergia sissoo* demonstrated particularly strong larvicidal activity against *Aedes aegypti*, indicating their promise as effective botanical alternatives to synthetic insecticides. These results underscore the value of exploring plant-based solutions for mosquito control, not only as a means to reduce environmental and health risks associated with chemical pesticides, but also as a sustainable approach that leverages locally available bioresources. Furthermore, this research lays the groundwork for future studies focused on isolating active phytochemicals, understanding their mechanisms of action, and evaluating their practical application in field settings.

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